

Gender Bias In Land Ownership In The Agricultural Sector

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Abstract

In the case of property rights, there is a huge disparity between men and women, women have less access to property as compared to men. Gender inequality in land rights is a global issue. Although the Constitution provides equal rights to men and women in property, the ground reality presents a different picture. Land ownership is mainly a male-dominated area. There are many factors preventing women from acquiring their property rights. Women have very few opportunities to live their life at their will and they don't have the right to make decisions at home or the workplace due to gender discrimination in property ownership, wages, and education. The Hindu Succession Act 2005 has given women the right to equality, according to which the daughter has the same property rights as the son. But very few women in our country have land rights. Women who own land do not have the right to make decisions related to the purchase and sale of land, and farming, as all the decisions are taken by men of the house. Policy initiatives for women land rights have yielded the desirable results in favour of women but these initiatives are not enough for gender equality in land ownership. Lack of awareness among women results in low access to resources, hence the government needs to run awareness programs for women concerning their rights to ownership of land.

Keywords

Agriculture, Property Rights, Gender Inequality, Awareness, Household.

Introduction

In underdeveloped and developed countries, gender inequalities are prevalent to a large extent. It is present in different forms and degrees. In the case of property rights, there is a huge disparity between men and women, women have less access to property as compared to men. Gender inequality in land is a global issue. Although the Constitution provides equal rights to men and women in property, the ground reality presents a different picture. Land ownership is mainly a male-dominated area. If we look at the property and inheritance laws of all countries, we find that in some countries there are many factors preventing women from acquiring their property ownership. In such type of countries, women have very few opportunities to live life freely and they don't have the right to make decisions at home or at the workplace due to gender discrimination in property ownership, wages, and education. They face domestic violence. The existence of gender inequality in agricultural households especially in male-headed families. Most decisions regarding control of money, the future of children, allocation and use of household resources such as labour, land, human capital resources, household spending, and so on are entirely taken by the males. Preference is given to male children, and women are less educated than men. Women are paid less wages as compared to their male counterparts. Indian society is male-dominated where a son is considered an asset and a daughter is considered a liability. The daughter does not have the right to property like the son. But the situation differs in different countries. Some countries give equal rights of wages and property to women and men. This is the reason that in these countries, women are economically independent and are making huge contributions toward economic development.

No doubt in India gender inequalities is prevalent to a large extent but our constitution provides equal rights to all genders. Some initiatives of the government and constitution to promote gender equality are:

1. Fundamental right to equality: In our constitution fundamental right to equality, articles (14 to 18) treat everybody equally, and any kind of discrimination based on religion, caste, gender, and birthplace is not allowed.
2. The Hindu Succession Act: This act applies to Hindus, Buddhists, Jains, Sikhs, Aarya and Brahmin. The Hindu Succession Act (1956) was amended in 2005.

According to the act, women are given the right to equality and the daughter has the same rights as the son in property.

3. Government is providing for ancestral many schemes and programmes for gender equality like Beti Bachao Beti Padhao, Mahila Shakti Kendra, Sukanya Samridhi Yojana, Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana, and Gender Budget.

Despite the constitution granting equality to men and women, the grassroots realities are harsh and women are not given equality at any level. Very few women have rights to ownership of land and women who are the owners of the land do not have the right to make decisions related to the purchase and sale of land and farming and all these decisions are taken by men

Objective of study The objective of this paper is to analyse the gender inequality in property rights in the agricultural sector.

Review of Literature

Chowdhry Prem (1997) in a paper based on a study in Haryana, found that although present-day women have equal property rights in our constitution, the ground fact is that women have less property ownership than men. Although they are well aware of their legal property rights, they do not claim their rights.

Tabitha Wagithi Kiriti and Clem Tisdell (2003) examine the gender inequality in the agriculture sector in Kenya. He found that more gender inequality exists in male-headed households. In male-headed families, most of the decisions were taken by males. Women have less decision-making power as compared to men.

Dalbir Singh (2004) found that women-headed households existed because of three reasons. These reasons are widowhood, irresponsible husband, and husband working outside. Women perform all the duties as heads of family and make all the decisions in the absence of their husbands.

Gautam P. Kanani (2020) in his paper titled "Role of Women in Agriculture" found that although women are major contributors to the workforce in agriculture, there is an existing gender gap. only a negligible portion of the women have land in their name. The role of women in the agriculture sector is largely ignored. Women are discriminated against and face many problems like lower wages, lack of property ownership, lack of resources, and more working hours as compared to men.

Methodology This paper is based on secondary data. Secondary data has been collected from books, journals, magazines, newspapers, and the Internet.

Analysis

Operational Holder

Estimated number of male and female operational holders

Sr. No.	State/Country	Female	Male	Total
		Number (in'000)	Number (in'000)	Number (in'000)
1	Haryana	240	1371	1611
2	India	20439	125751	146190

Sources: Agriculture census 2015-16

According to the table, in Haryana female operational holders are 14.89 percent and males are 85.1 percent. In India, the percentage of female and male operational holders was about 13.98 and 86.02 percent respectively. This shows the huge disparity between men and women, women operational holders are far less as compared to men.

Gender inequality in Land Rights

Land is an important asset in the agriculture sector for production. Land ownership gives decision-making power to landholders regarding the use of land, crop pattern, sale and purchase, and transfer of land. Globally, Women landlords are less than 15 percent of all landlords according to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations and 85 percent men are landlords.

Suggestion

1. Development programs play an important role in women empowerment. Policies and laws for gender equality in land rights are working well on paper but ground realities are vice versa. There is huge gender inequality in the right to land. Government needs to make new policies and improve old policies to reach the target of gender equality and women empowerment.
2. To promote gender equality in land ownership in Haryana, there is a two percent concession in stamp duty if the property is registered in the name of women. Stamp duty for women is two percent less as compared to men. However, these types of schemes are not enough to promote gender equality because women are less aware of land rights. Lack of awareness among women resulted in low access to the resources and institutional support provided by the government this needs due attention of the policymakers and planners for improvement. The problem of the gender gap in land rights can be solved by making women aware of their rights and government programs. Hence the government needs to run awareness programmes for women in the rural sector.
3. To achieve gender equality in land rights, the government needs to eliminate all forms of gender inequalities like inequality in wages, inequality regarding employment opportunities, and inequalities in basic facilities such as education, medical, and nutrition. Since these inequalities are inter-related they need to be tackled with a colossal effort.

Conclusion

The conclusions of the study are as follows:

1. Policy initiatives for women land rights have yielded the desirable results in favor of women but these initiatives are not enough for gender equality in land rights.
2. There is provision of legal rights given to women by the constitution but the ground reality is far from that.
3. women are the major contributors to agricultural operations, but they are deprived of the benefits of agricultural development.
4. Lack of awareness among women resulted in low access to resources. They have limited access and control over resources.
5. Limited access of women to land holding may be because of social constraints.
6. Two percent concessions in stamp duty in the land transfers in favour of women have yielded some positive outcomes. Such concessions resulted in enhancing the social mindset towards control over resources by women, but we are still far behind in granting equality to the fair sex in terms of access to land resources and this needs the due attention of policymakers.

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